

ArrayAnalysis and PinPath: Unlocking the Full Potential of Omics Data

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1. Introduction

Omics technologies have become indispensable in biomedical research for uncovering molecular mechanisms and identifying biomarkers. However, current analysis pipelines often lack accessibility to non-expert users and generate complex outputs that are difficult to interpret. To address these limitations, we have developed two complementary tools: **ArrayAnalysis**, a user-friendly platform for transcriptomics data analysis, and **PinPath**, an R package and web application designed to facilitate the visualization of omics data onto biological pathways.

2. ArrayAnalysis

ArrayAnalysis (<https://ArrayAnalysis.org/>) is a platform, available as a web app, Desktop app, Docker image, and R package, that provides a streamlined and accessible workflow for the analysis of both **microarray** and **RNA-seq data** (Figure 1). ArrayAnalysis offers several innovations, including enhanced **user guidance** throughout the analysis steps, **interactive outputs** that facilitate data exploration, and **customizable figures** tailored for use in scientific publications. With these features, ArrayAnalysis aims to make transcriptomic data analysis more approachable and effective for a broad audience of biomedical researchers.

Figure 1. Overview of the ArrayAnalysis workflow. More information about ArrayAnalysis can be found on the website: <https://ArrayAnalysis.org/>.

3. PinPath

PinPath (<https://SyNUM-lab.github.io/PinPath-web/>) is an R package and web-based application for visualizing various omics data, such as genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics, onto pathway diagrams from **WikiPathways**¹, **KEGG**², and custom **GPML/KGML** files. These visualizations enable researchers to go beyond pathway statistics and explore where changes occur within pathways. PinPath supports the simultaneous visualization of multiple

variables (e.g., log₂FC and statistical significance; see **Figure 2**) as well as the integration of multi-omics datasets.

Figure 2. Differential gene expression results plotted on the Non-small cell lung cancer (WP4255) pathway using PinPath.

4. Conclusion

By providing a streamlined and user-friendly interface for transcriptomics data analysis, ArrayAnalysis serves a broad scientific audience, ranging from researchers with limited bioinformatics experience seeking guided support to experts in need of an accessible platform for **fast, reproducible, and standardized analyses**. Complementary, PinPath supports the interpretation, enabling researchers to **pinpoint where changes occur** within pathways. Together, ArrayAnalysis and PinPath empower researchers to unlock the full potential of their omics data.

References

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